

Innovation Actions Description								
Type of Innovation								
Needs Addressed								
		Impact Assessment -Horizontal Dimensions						
		Individual Directions Addressed (√)	Extent of Application (Local, Regional, National, International, Individual)	Influence				
Type (Direct, Indirect)	Quality (Positive, Negative)							
Impact Assessment Dimensions - Vertical Dimensions	PS Modernization (I)	Institutional / Capacity Development	Degree of Resources (Capital, Personnel, Infrastructure) Utilization					
			Efficiency / Productivity					
			Sustainability					
			Cross-organization Cooperation					
			Quality of Services Provided					
		Image Modernization						
		Political	Level of Participation					
			Transparency					
			Creation of Trust & Confidence					
			PS as an Innovation Driver (II)	Economical	Productivity (Labor / Capital / Resource) & Growth			
	Entrepreneurship							
	Innovation							
	Social	Employment						
		Prosperity & Well-being						
		Quality of Education						
		Quality of Health						
	Infrastructural	Equity & Inclusiveness						
		Privacy & Security						
		Public Safety						
		Transport Infrastructure						
Environmental	ICT Infrastructure							
	e-Security							
	Quality of the Biosphere							
	Energy Consumption - Natural Resources Utilization							
Environmental Awareness Creation								